

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

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- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“ANINO”

Himig ng katahimikan
Binubulong ng isipan
Mundo’y pilit hinihipan
Saliw na naghahalinhinan

Ingay na tinatalikdan
Iniwasan at ipinagpaliban
Mahirap gayong labanan
Kusa itong sinusundan

Hinigian ng tulong
Pusong may dunong
Napuno ng pulong
Sarili’y maging salong

Huwag na ikubli
Makamtan na muli
Liwang sa huli
Mapaghingan kahit dagli

Itaas na gabay
Puro at tunay

Malaya bilang alay
Isanggalang sariling bantay

